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APPLICATION FORMS IN FAMILY COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. In the article, the application forms in family communication were considered. The socio-psychological characteristics of the family members, their personal qualities, and the unique characteristics of the language personality are shown in the lexicon of each family. In the lexicon of different families, there are general and specific. The identity is related to the traditions of the family, its composition and structure, socio-psychological and age characteristics of the family members, and the characteristics of their language characteristics. The concept of family etiquette is ambiguous: on the one hand, it is a set of rules for behavior in the family, and on the other hand, it is cultural family foundations. The rules of etiquette of different families have a common and specific feature. Determining the criteria for good speech in the family is of practical importance for everyone, and learning about it helps to improve the speech culture of society.

Key words: family communication, features, forms of address, spiritual world, common customs and family traditions.

In linguistics, the concept of family communication has not received the status of a term and does not have its own definition. Family communication is known differently: "language within the family"; "home language", "family dialect", "family language". The composition of these names includes a group of words in different word forms. In linguistics and explanatory dictionaries, this word refers to the word family and is interpreted as "a group of close relatives living together." In their works, L.P. Krisin and A.V. Znadvorova define the family as "a small social group whose members are united by common activities and have direct personal contact, based on the values and norms of behavior, which are the basis for the emergence of emotional relationships both in the group and in the special group", based on the definition [2, 17].

M.N. Rasulov said that the family "has a certain attitude to someone's word, opinion", it "contrasts someone's word to the world, to someone else's word as something united, the commonality of views and evaluations of local people connects with" [1, 102].

The concept of "family" has its own national characteristics. For a European, the concept of my family is narrower than for an Uzbek, because it includes only husband, wife and their children. In the Uzbek language, according to this

concept, it means not only wife, children, parents, but also grandmother, grandfather, brothers, sisters, pets, if they live together.

When defining a family, it is necessary to pay attention to the personal relationship of its members, their cohabitation and household work. On this basis, family communication can be called communication of relatives who live together. In this case, the names "within the family" and "house" are used as complete synonyms of the word "family". Communication between relatives who do not live together can be called communication between relatives.

Thus, family as a group of relatives living together, as well as taking into account its national characteristics, we will consider that family communication and communication of relatives are special types of everyday communication.

The language of the family is the language in which the closest people communicate. No one specially develops his vocabulary, but he is very dynamic and quickly responds to any changes in the life of the speakers. This "language" exists within the family and is understood only by the members of that family. It forms the spiritual world, a means of communication between people united by common customs and family traditions. It is in such an environment of mutual understanding that a special non-closed "language" is created and lives, as it constantly replenishes its lexical and phraseological composition. It depends not only on the character, temperament, age, and profession of family members. Each new situation in the life of relatives can be the reason for the accidental creation of a new speech unit, distinguished by its expressive color and emotion. At the same time, native speakers themselves often do not recognize themselves as creators and do not feel the semantic, phonetic or grammatical strangeness of the element of communicative speech they create.

As the main form of communication in the family, the family language has certain speech functions, which are manifested in the usual, that is, daily, interactions between family members. For example, G. Rasulova notes three main functions:

- communicative (function of communication);
- game (the struggle against the monotony of everyday life and the desire to create special language tools that are specific to this micro-collective and distinguish it from other language environments);
- the "secret language" function (the family dialect is closed; it is used only between family members).

Dictionary of the language of the family according to the materials of different families described in P.P. Chaykovskiy, B.Yu. Kamolova, A.V. Davronov's works.

Research has identified common characteristics common to all families and characteristics unique to a particular family. The uniqueness is related to the traditions of the family, its composition and structure, socio-psychological and age characteristics of the family members. The socio-psychological characteristics of the family members, their personal qualities, and the unique characteristics of the language personality are reflected in the lexicon of each family.

In many families, there is an environment of family language play. According to researchers of Uzbek colloquial speech, tendency to play language is a characteristic of intellectuals [3]. In some families, a characteristic feature of the language is the use of expressions of literary origin. Other sources of family phraseology are popular songs and movie jokes, as well as proverbs and proverbs.

The main methods of the speech game are used by all members of the family. It can be a deliberate violation of the harmony of words, combining stylistically incompatible words in a single statement.

Family language is, as a rule, a system of multilevel linguistic tools that exists in friendly families with stable traditions of speech behavior. Let's give some examples. Thus, there are often lexical units obtained by the following methods of word formation:

Playing with words in family communication is not a deviation from the norm. "In everyday speech, language games are usually taken as a normal positive phenomenon. It shines with joyful sparks in the daily lively communication of people" [4].

In family communication, the mother's speech is characterized by increased emotionality, in this regard, we note another feature of the language in the family - the active use of evaluative, modal words and intensive words: undoubtedly, without words (as answers); very talented; nightmare; beautiful; huge and others.

From time to time, the mother repeats stories - "plates": stories that are repeated verbatim - memories of events in the children's childhood. Family members use their language mainly at home, in a family environment. Some words are sometimes broken in the presence of relatives or strangers, causing misunderstanding on the one hand, and interest on the other.

Thus, we can talk about the existence of the language unit of the family, the existence of boundaries in the use of the family language, the difference between

one's own family members and others, and the specific characteristics of each individual family language.

The uniqueness of the family language is determined by the composition of the family, the personal qualities of the speakers, their gender, psychological characteristics, and the profession of the family members.

A distinctive feature of family communication is the traditional distribution of family roles, family hierarchy. A person begins to master his first social roles from the very beginning of his life. The main family roles (husband and wife, mother and father, children) and their speech expression are studied in the article.

E.F. Tarasov, V.I. Belikov, L.P. Krisin and other researchers have written about statuses and roles. These roles represent hierarchical inequalities. By creating a family, people acquire new roles, the main of which are the roles of husband and wife, father and mother. With the development of the family, the emergence of new family relationships, the set of family roles expands: the roles of grandparents, father-in-law and mother-in-law, bride and groom, etc. appear. The diversity of family roles determines the polyglossia nature of family communication, by A.V. Nodirov.

Thus, family roles are the result of syncretism and the establishment of different roles (hierarchical, psychological, initiative) performed by family members, which have their own verbal expression in the field of family communication. It is impossible to evaluate family communication from the point of view of compliance with the standards of speech culture and communication standards, from the point of view of rhetoric, without taking into account both the main and the role in each case.

In family communication, a person's professional affiliation (in particular, his military service) is manifested, which can affect the course of family communication [5]. The socio-psychological characteristics and personal qualities of the family members are shown in the lexicon of each family. In the lexicon of different families, there are general and specific. The identity is related to the traditions of the family, its composition and structure, socio-psychological and gender and age characteristics of the family members, and the characteristics of their language characteristics.

The concept of family etiquette is ambiguous: on the one hand, it is a set of rules for behavior in the family, and on the other hand, it is cultural family foundations. More polite (compared to family communication) is

communication between relatives. The rules of etiquette of different families have a common and specific feature.

There is a difference between the language unit of the family, the limits of the use of the language of the family, the members of one's own family, and so on. The language of each family is unique and has its own characteristics. The uniqueness of the family language is determined by the composition of the family, the personal qualities of the speakers, their gender, psychological characteristics, and the professional affiliation of the family members.

The nature of family communication is determined by the traditional division of family roles, the family hierarchy. Each family role has its own characteristics, its own speech manifestation.

Considering the role of the mother, we found out the uniqueness of the speech, which depends on the family functions she performs, which is clearly manifested at different levels of language and communication, especially at the genre-thematic and lexical levels. The formation of mother's communication skills happens gradually. A mother's verbal communication with small children is fundamentally different from the communication with adult children that is required.

The main criterion of a good speech in relation to the field of family communication is to consider its effectiveness while observing the standards of literary language and the ethics of communication. Qualities of a good speech, such as vocabulary, accuracy, consistency, correctness, are the necessary criteria for defining a speech as good. A good family speech helps to achieve mutual understanding, mutual respect, avoid quarrels and conflicts, and therefore helps to save the family.

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